

Kinetics and Mechanism of the Dissociation of Heterochelate Complexes. Acid-Catalyzed Dissociation of *Bis*-Biguanide *Mono*-Acetylacetonato-, and *Bis*-Biguanide *Mono*-Phenylbiguanide-Cobalt(III) Complexes.

B. CHAKRAVARTY* and A. K. SIL

Department of Chemistry; Inorganic Chemistry Laboratories, Kalyani University, Kalyani-741 235

Acid catalyzed dissociation of two mixed chelate complexes, *bis*-biguanide-*mono*-acetylacetonato- and *bis*-biguanide-*mono*-phenylbiguanide-cobalt(III) perchlorate were investigated spectrophotometrically. These complexes dissociate in a stepwise manner. The first step of dissociation occurs around room temperature (30° - 40°) and in presence of 0.03 - 0.3M HClO₄. Only one biguanide is released at this stage with the formation of diaquo-monobiguanide complexes. These later complexes above 50° and in presence of 0.5M HClO₄ or more further dissociate with the release of the second 'biguanide'. Activation parameters for the 1st stage are $\Delta H^{\ddagger}_{aac}$ 15.0 k cal. mole⁻¹, $\Delta H^{\ddagger}_{phB}$ 15.4 k cal. mole⁻¹ and $\Delta S^{\ddagger}_{aac}$ -21 e. u.; $\Delta S^{\ddagger}_{phB}$ -20 e. u.; and for the IInd stage $\Delta H^{\ddagger}_{aac}$ 19.3 k cal. mole⁻¹; $\Delta H^{\ddagger}_{phB}$ 20.2 k cal. mole⁻¹ and $\Delta S^{\ddagger}_{aac}$ -19 e.u.; $\Delta S^{\ddagger}_{phB}$ 17 e.u. (The subscripts 'aac' and 'phB' denote the acetylacetonato- and phenylbiguanide complexes respectively) The mechanism appears to involve the dissociation of a protonated 'BigH', with simultaneous bond formation by an incoming watermolecule in the transition state.

ACID catalyzed dissociations of metal chelates have been well investigated¹. In mixed chelate complexes, containing ligands which dissociate in acid solution as a result of protonation, a competition for protonation between the ligands may control the overall mechanism of the reaction. Literature contains few scattered studies on such reactions, mostly with multidentate amines and oxalate²⁻⁵ or carbonate⁶ chelates. Present investigation was undertaken to study systematically the acid catalyzed dissociations of mixed chelate complexes of cobalt(III). In this investigation, two complex compounds, *bis*-biguanide-*mono*-acetylacetonato and *bis*-biguanide-*mono*-phenylbiguanide cobalt(III) perchlorates, [Co(BigH)₂(aac)](ClO₄)₂ and [Co(BigH)₂(PhBigH)](ClO₄)₂ were undertaken. It is known^{7,8} that in presence of acid, the dissociation of these ligands is acid-catalyzed. Our objective was to find how acid catalyzation takes place in a competitive manner and influence the stepwise removal of these chelates.

Experimental

Preparation of the complex :

1. *Bis*-biguanide-*mono*-acetylacetonatocobalt(III) perchlorate.

The corresponding chloride was prepared by the method of Dutta and Sarkar.⁹ When a saturated solution of sodium perchlorate was added to a concentrated solution of complex chloride and cooled in ice, reddish pink crystals of the perchlorate separate out. This complex has a low solubility in water.

Analysis : Found—Co-10.32; N-24.71%. Calculated for [Co(C₂H₇N₅)₂(C₅H₇O₂)](ClO₄)₂, Co-10.54; N-25.0%.

2. *Bis*-biguanide-*mono*-phenylbiguanidecobalt(III) perchlorate.

The corresponding complex sulphate was prepared by the method of Dutta and Sarkar⁹, from which the perchlorate was obtained by metathesis with barium perchlorate. It was once more crystallized before use.

Analysis : Found—Co-8.03; N-18.82%. Calculated for [Co(C₂H₇N₅)₂(C₆H₅C₂H₅N₅)](ClO₄)₂, Co-8.0; N-19.0%.

All other reagents used were of reagent quality or else purified by suitable methods. Distilled water redistilled in an all-glass apparatus was used for making the solutions. The rate of acid catalyzed dissociation was measured spectrophotometrically with a Beckman DU-2 spectrophotometer. Kinetic runs were carried out in a stoppered Jena volumetric flask, placed in a thermostat, where the temperature was held to within $\pm 0.1^\circ$ of the desired value. 3 ml portion of the reacting solution was withdrawn at required intervals, quenched by putting in a test tube dipped in iced-water around 5° and quickly measured for absorbance in a stoppered silica cell.

The spectra of a series of solutions of each of these complexes ($1 \times 10^{-3} M$) containing different amounts of acid (HClO₄) varying from 0 to 1 M were recorded immediately after preparation and after 2, 4, 6 hrs., 1, 2, 3 ... days upto two weeks. In case of acetylacetonato complex, for all the acid ranges studied, there is an initial change in the absorption and for the

acid ranges, 0.01-0.1 M, it remains unchanged after a day at room temperature, indicating the formation of diaquo-*mono*-biguanide-*mono*-acetylacetonato complex, which is stable in this acid range at room temperature. This diaquo-complex, in presence of 0.2M and higher acid concentrations further dissociates to tetraaquo-complex (?) which spontaneously decomposes to Co^{2+} . BigH and acacH (acacH=acetylacetonate) at a much slower rate, without affecting the pseudo-unimolecular rate determination for the dissociation of the title complex for 5-6 half lives. In the case of phenylbiguanide complex, it has been observed in this way that in the acid ranges, 0.01-0.1 M HClO_4 , the final spectra recorded is identical with that of the diaquo-*mono*-biguanide-*mono*-phenylbiguanidecobalt(III) ion. Fig. 1 records the spectra of 0.001 M solutions of the

Fig. 1

Figure 1: Absorption spectra of 0.001 M aqueous solutions of various complex ions (absorbance per cm).

- (a) (1) $\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_2(\text{acac})_2^{2+}$, (2) $\text{Co}(\text{BigH})(\text{acac})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2^{2+}$;
 (b) (1) $\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_2(\text{PhBigH})_2^{2+}$, (2) $\text{Co}(\text{BigH})(\text{PhBigH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2^{2+}$.

(BigH=biguanide, PhBigH=Phenylbiguanide, acacH=acetylacetonate).

experimental complexes and their first dissociation products, the diaquo-*mono*-biguanide-*mono*-acetylacetonato and diaquo-*mono*-biguanide-*mono*-phenylbiguanide ions. At a temperature around 60°, in presence of 0.2-2.0 M HClO_4 , this complex further decomposes to Co^{2+} , BigH and PhBigH. (BigH=Biguanide and PhBigH=Phenylbiguanide molecules). The release of

biguanide in both the complexes takes place in stages, the conditions being wide apart in acidity and temperature. The pseudo-unimolecular rate measurements for each stage can easily be made, without any interference with the other. The rates of reactions were studied under various conditions of acid concentration and temperature. The pseudo-first order rate constants for each stage were evaluated graphically by the method of Guggenheim¹⁰ by plotting $-\log(A_t - A_{t+\tau})$ vs time, where τ denotes a constant time interval. The wave lengths for absorbance measurements were 500 nm and 480 nm respectively for acetylacetonate and phenylbiguanide complexes, where the differences in absorbance between the reactants and products are maximum.

Identification of the dissociation products :

1. Aqueation of $\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_2(\text{acac})^{2+}$

When 500 ml of a 1×10^{-3} M solution of the complex in 0.05 M HNO_3 was aquated for 24 hrs. at room temperature and concentrated in a rotary evaporator to a small volume (ca. 5 ml), an orange-red compound was obtained. Aqueation reactions were carried out in presence of HNO_3 , because of the convenience of evaporation under reduced pressure. The orange-red compound was dissolved in little water and allowed to crystallize in air. Beautiful orange-red crystals of the diaquo-complex were obtained.

Analysis: Found: N-23.71; Co-14.52; H_2O -9.00. Calculated for $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})(\text{acac})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2](\text{NO}_3)_2$, N-23.4; Co-14.09; H_2O -8.59.

When the aqueation reaction was carried out at 50° in presence of 0.5M acid, on concentration in a rotary evaporator, Co^{2+} ion, 'biguanide' as nitrate and acetylacetonate were obtained. Co^{2+} ion was identified by α -nitroso- β -naphthol spot test, free acetylacetonate was estimated by *o*-phenylenediamine in acid media¹³ and the 'biguanide' as the copper complex in ammoniacal media.

2. Aqueation of $\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_2(\text{PhBigH})^{2+}$

After completion of the aqueation reaction in presence of 0.05M HNO_3 at room temperature, 500 ml of the solution was completely evaporated in a rotary evaporator. The residue was then taken with a little water and a saturated solution of ammonium sulphate was added and cooled in a freezing mixture, when the orange-red diaquo-sulphate $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})(\text{PhBigH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2](\text{SO}_4)_2$ was obtained. It was further purified by recrystallization.

Analysis: Found—N-27.41; Co-10.92; H_2O -7.21. Calculated for the diaquo-complex—N-27.09; Co-11.41; H_2O -6.97.

When the aqueation of the title complex was carried out at 80° in presence of 1.0 M HNO_3 , the dissociation products were obtained as Co^{2+} ion, identified as before and biguanide and phenylbiguanide as their nitrates. Biguanide and phenylbiguanide, were converted to their

copper complexes in mixed state. Nitrogen estimation ($N=45.3\%$) indicated their proportion as 2 : 1.

None of the diaquo complex, obtained as intermediate in aquations, loses any significant amount of their weights before 180° . This indicates, both the water molecules are coordinated with metal atom.

Results and Discussion

The pseudo-first order rate constants, k_{obs} , for both the complexes, in each stage of dissociation, were found to vary with the concentration of acid. The rate does not change with different amounts of complex, and hence its first order dependence on complex is established. Table-I records different k_{obs} values

Figure 2: Effect of acid on rate of dissociation at different temperatures.

(a) $\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_2(\text{acac})_2^{2+}$, (b) $\text{Co}(\text{BigH})(\text{acac})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2^{2+}$.

(c) $\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_2(\text{PhBigH})_2^{2+}$, (d) $\text{Co}(\text{BigH})(\text{PhBigH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2^{2+}$
(BigH = biguanide, PhBigH = phenylbiguanide, acacH = acetylacetonate)

TABLE I—DEPENDENCE OF THE RATE OF DISSOCIATION OF $\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_2(\text{ACAC})_2^{2+}$ AND $\text{Co}(\text{BigH})(\text{PhBigH})_2^{2+}$ ON ACID CONCENTRATION. $[\text{COMPLEX}] = 1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$

First-stage of dissociation Complex	Temp. °C	$[\text{HClO}_4], \text{ M}$					(second order rate const.) ($k_2 \text{ min}^{-1}$)
		0.03	0.05	0.08	0.10	0.15	
$\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_2(\text{acac})_2^{2+}$ $10^3 k \text{ min}^{-1}$ $\mu = 0.2 \text{ M}$	30		0.6	1.8	-2.3	3.1	0.21
	35	0.76	1.34	2.33	2.90		0.285
	40	2.2	2.7	3.9	5.3		0.53
$\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_2(\text{PhBigH})_2^{2+}$ $10^3 k \text{ min}^{-1}$ $\mu = 0.5 \text{ M}$	29.5		1.71	2.6	3.22	4.19	0.17
	35		2.3	3.85	5.16	7.48	0.26
	38	2.07	3.64	6.15	8.0		0.395
Second-stage of dissociation		$[\text{HClO}_4], \text{ M}$					$(10^3 k_2 \text{ min}^{-1})$
		0.5	0.7	1.0			
$\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_2(\text{acac})_2^{2+}$ $10^3 k \text{ min}^{-1}$ $\mu = 1 \text{ M}$	50	1.54	2.49	3.26			3.25
	55	2.30	3.22	4.45			4.60
	60	4.40	5.76	7.58			7.90
		$[\text{HClO}_4], \text{ M}$					$(10^3 k_2' \text{ min}^{-1})$
		0.5	0.7	0.8	1.0	1.5	
$\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_2(\text{PhBigH})_2^{2+}$ $10^3 k \text{ min}^{-1}$ $\mu = 1.5 \text{ M}$	55	1.23	1.79		2.84		2.8
	60	2.70	3.36	3.97	4.9		4.9
	65	4.15	6.2		8.32		8.3

obtained at various acid concentrations and temperature but with fixed ionic concentrations (μ). A plot of k_{obs} versus $[H^+]$, (figure 2a,b,c,d) where $[H^+]$ is the concentration of the strong acid used, gives a straight line in each case, also showing first-order dependence of rate on $[H^+]$. These lines pass through origin and indicate, the dissociations proceed only through an acid-dependent path, with virtually no contribution by any acid independent path. From the slopes of these plots, the second order rate constants (k_1 and k_2 for 'acac' complex and k_1' and k_2' for 'PhBigH' complex) at various temperatures were calculated and are also reported in Table-1.

1. Aqueation of $Co(BigH)_2(acac)^{2+}$

On the basis of the reaction products obtained during the aqueation and the first-order dependence of rate on $[H^+]$ for each stage of dissociation, the mechanism of aqueation may be proposed as :

As 'biguanide' is more basic ($pK_1 = 12.5$ at 32°) than 'acac', protonation of the 'biguanide' takes place before 'acac'. Protonation takes place at the free basic = NH group⁷. This develops a strain in the chelate ring, with ultimate rupture of it. Bond rupture processes are same for both stages of 'BigH' release. Tetraaquo-complexes of cobalt(III) being unstable in aqueous solution, decompose immediately as soon as it is formed.

-2. Aqueation of $Co(BigH)_2(PhBigH)^{3+}$

In this case also, the first-order dependence of rate on $[H^+]$ for each stage of aqueation and the reaction products obtained during the reaction lead to conclude the mechanism as :

The process of 'bond rupture' is similar to that of acetylacetonato complex.

On the basis of the above mechanisms the rate of dissociation of either complex, in each stage of dissociation, may be given by Rate = k [conjugate acid] = kK

[complex] $[H^+] = k^*$ [complex] $[H]$, where k^* is the second-order rate constant, 'K' is the equilibrium constant for the formation of the protonated species (conjugate acid), and 'k' is the rate constant for the slow rate determining step. 'K' is assumed to be very small, so that $[I] \gg [II]$. $[I]$ = concentration of any complex species and $[II]$ = the concentration of its conjugate acid.

The effect of ionic strength (μ) on the rates of dissociation, at a definite acid strength and temperature, is given in Table 2. The rate of dissociation increases with ionic concentration as expected in such cases.

Activation parameters, for each stage of aqueation, have been evaluated graphically (Fig. 3) in the usual way, making use of Eyring equation¹⁰ and are given in Table 3 along with few other similar "biguanide" complexes. For the 1st stage of aqueation, the ΔH^\ddagger values for these two complexes are nearly the same as other bis-biguanide complexes, showing the chelate-bonds are of equal strength and similar processes operate in the release of a "BigH" in each case. However, the greater reactivity of these complexes over to $Co(BigH)_2$ -

Figure 3 : Effect of temperature on rate of dissociation
 (1) $Co(BigH)_2(acac)^{2+}$ ($\mu=0.2$), (2) $Co(BigH)_2(PhBigH)^{2+}$ ($\mu=0.5$)
 (3) $Co(BigH)(acac)(H_2O)_2^{2+}$ ($\mu=1$)
 (4) $Co(BigH)(PhBigH)(H_2O)_2^{2+}$ ($\mu=1.5$)

$(H_2O)_3^{2+}$, is entropy controlled. The less negative ΔS^\ddagger values for these two complexes as well as for *trans*- $Co(BigH)_2(CN)_2^+$ show that they are less solvated in the transition state than $Co(BigH)_2(H_2O)_3^{2+}$, though other factors may also be responsible to lower the ΔS^\ddagger values. In the dissociation of biguanide com-

TABLE 2—DEPENDENCE OF THE RATE OF DISSOCIATION OF THE FIRST STAGE OF THE COMPLEX ON IONIC STRENGTH (μ)

Co (BigH) ₂ (acac) ²⁺	$-1 \times 10^{-3} M$,	HClO ₄ ,	$5 \times 10^{-2} M$;	Temp, 35°
' μ ' M	0.05	0.10	0.15	0.20
10 ³ k, min ⁻¹	11	12	13.6	17.7
Co (BigH) ₂ (PhBigH) ²⁺	$-1 \times 10^{-3} M$,	HClO ₄ ,	0.1 M ;	Temp, 29.5°
' μ ' M	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.5
10 ³ k, min ⁻¹	16.8	18	20	21.6

TABLE 3—ACTIVATION PARAMETERS OF SOME COBALT(III)—BIGUANIDE COMPLEX (FOR SUBSTITUTION OF TWO 'AQUA' LIGANDS FOR A BIGUANIDE)

Complex	ΔH^\ddagger k cal, mole ⁻¹	ΔS^\ddagger e. u.	References
Co (BigH) ₃ ³⁺	11.1	-31.5	7
cis-Co (BigH) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂ ³⁺	15.2	-31.6	12
trans-Co (BigH) ₂ (CN) ₂ ³⁺	15.6	-24	12
Co (BigH) ₂ (acac) ²⁺	15.0	-21	This work
Co (BigH) ₂ (PhBigH) ²⁺	15.4	-20	"
Co ₂ (BigH) ₂ (acac) (H ₂ O) ₂ ³⁺	19.3	-19	"
Co (BigH) (PhBigH) (H ₂ O) ₂ ³⁺	20.2	-17	"

plexes, the departure of a 'BigH' is assisted by the attack of two H₂O molecules from the opposite directions. The ΔH^\ddagger values for the second-stage of dissociation of these two complexes, that is for the *mono*-biguanide complexes, are nearly equal and differ from that of 1st stage, by 4-5 k calories. ΔS^\ddagger values for the first and second stages of dissociation, are nearly equal showing similar mechanisms for the formation of 'transition state' for the release of first and second 'EigH'. The greater rate of the release of first 'BigH' is due to lower ΔH^\ddagger value. It is interesting to note, the differences in the ΔH^\ddagger values for the dissociations of a 'biguanide', between *tris*- and *bis*- and *bis*- and *mono*-biguanide complexes are about 4 k calories. As the number of 'biguanide' chelates decreases, the more efficient donation of electrons by other remaining 'biguanides' make stronger bonds, with consequent greater energies for bond rupture. The overall charge of the *bis*-complexes reported in Table 3 differs widely, but the ΔH^\ddagger values for each stage are nearly the same. The near independence of the ΔH^\ddagger values on the overall charge on the complex suggests that probably 'bond formation' and 'bond breaking' are both important in the transition state. The mechanism thus appears to be one which involves the dissociation of a protonated 'BigH' from the conjugate acid of the complex with simultaneous 'bond formation' by an incoming water molecule.

Acknowledgement

Authors wish to express their gratitude to the authorities of Kalvani University for providing a Junior Research Scholarship to one of them (A.K.S.).

References

1. F. BASOLO and R. G. PEARSON—"Mechanisms of Inorganic Reactions", 2nd Ed. J. Wiley & Sons, Inc. New York. Chapter 3.
2. M. B. DAVIES and J. W. LETHBRIDGE *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1975, 37(1), 175.
3. C. ANDRADE and H. TAUBE, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 86 1328.
4. D. BANERJEA and S. SENGUPTA, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1973, 397, 215.
5. J. M. VEIGEL, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1968, 7(1), 69.
6. D. J. FRANCIS and G. H. SEARLE, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1974, 27(2), 269.
7. D. BANERJEA and B. CHAKRAVARTY, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1964, 26, 1233.
8. D. BANERJEA and S. DUTTACHAUDHURI, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1971, 33, 515.
9. R. L. DUTTA and S. Sarkar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1967, 44, 832.
10. E. A. GUGGENHEIM, *Phil. Mag.*, 1926, 538.
11. S. GLASSTONE, K. J. LAIDLER and H. EYRING, "The theory of Rate Processes.", McGraw-Hill, New York 1941.
12. B. CHAKRAVARTY and A. K. SIL, Unpublished work.
13. J. AGGETT and A. L. ODELL, *J. Chem. Soc.*, A, 1966, 1820.